

Household WASH CRF

#	Question	Variable
1	Today's date	DD/MM/YYYY
2	Household ID	
Section 1: Toilet Data		
3	What type of toilet do you use?	Home: Flush/pour flush toilet to main sewer Home: Flush/pour flush toilet to septic tank Home: Pit latrine Home: Composting toilet Home: Bucket Home: Other (specify) Public toilet Shared toilet Other (specify) No toilet (go to Q17)
4	Toilet walls construction	Unbaked bricks Baked bricks Concrete blocks Metal sheets Reed mats Maize/plastic bags Other (specify)
5	Toilet floor construction	Cement Tile Carpet Wood Sand/soil Other (Specify)
6	Toilet roof construction	Metal sheets Plastic sheets Reed mats Thatched No roof
<i>Please observe/inspect the toilet inside and outside</i>		
7	Can the toilet be locked from the outside?	Yes No
8	Can the toilet be locked from the inside?	Yes No

9	Is there sign of faeces on the floor or walls of the toilet?	Yes No
10	Is there anal cleansing material inside the toilet?	Yes No (go to 11)
10a	If yes, what are they?"	Toilet paper Newspaper/paper Leaves Other (specify)
11	Where flies visible in the toilet?	Yes No
12	Is there a drop hole cover?	Yes No (go to Q13)
12a	Is the drop hole cover in place over the hole?	Yes No
13	How is the smell in the toilet?	No smell Slight smell Strong smell Unbearable smell
14	Walk around the perimeter of the household - do you see human faeces?	Yes - adult Yes- child Yes - unsure of source No
15	Walk around the perimeter of the household - do you see any animal faeces?	Yes No
16	Are animals near or inside the house?	Yes No (go to Q17)
16a	What animals?	Chickens Other poultry Goats Cows Pigs Dogs Cats Other (specify)
Section 2: Hand-washing Data		
17	Are there facilities for hand washing at the following? (answer for each A-E) A) Toilet B) Kitchen/food preparation area C) Household yard D) Inside house (other)	Yes No (go to Q18)

	E) Other (specify)	
17a	<p>What type of HWF is there? (answer for each A-E)</p> <p>A) Toilet B) Kitchen/food preparation area C) Household yard D) Inside house (other) E) Other (specify)</p>	<p>Tippy Tap Mug / cup Bucket Bucket with tap Jerry Can Tap with running water Other</p>
18	<p>Is there water in/at the HWF? (answer for each A-E)</p> <p>A) Toilet B) Kitchen/food preparation area C) Household yard D) Inside house (other) E) Other (specify)</p>	<p>Yes No (go to Q19)</p>
18a	<p>What is the source of the water supply? (answer for each A-E)</p> <p>A) Toilet B) Kitchen/food preparation area C) Household yard D) Inside house (other) E) Other (specify)</p>	<p>Piped water (direct) Water kiosk Borehole Shallow well River Other (specify)</p>
18b	<p>How is the water at the HWF? (answer for each A-E)</p> <p>A) Toilet B) Kitchen/food preparation area C) Household yard D) Inside house (other) E) Other (specify)</p>	<p>Visibly clear Visibly dirty</p>
19	<p>At the toilet, are there other materials for handwashing in addition to water?</p>	<p>Soap (bar) Soap (liquid) Soap (powder) Ash Sand Other (specify) None</p>
20	<p>At the kitchen/food preparation area, are there other materials</p>	<p>Soap (bar) Soap (liquid) Soap (powder)</p>

	for handwashing in addition to water?	Ash Sand Other (specify) None
21	At the household yard, are there other materials for handwashing in addition to water?	Soap (bar) Soap (liquid) Soap (powder) Ash Sand Other (specify) None
22	Inside the house, are there other materials for handwashing in addition to water?	Soap (bar) Soap (liquid) Soap (powder) Ash Sand Other (specify) None
23	Is there a bathroom?	Bathing Room (exterior) Bathing room (interior) Latrine Other (specify)
Section 3: Water Supply		
24	Is water stored in the house?	Yes No
25	How is drinking water stored?	Plastic bucket no lid Plastic bucket with lid Plastic bucket with tap and no lid Plastic bucket with lid and tap Metal bucket (ndowa) covered Metal bucket (ndowa) uncovered Clay pot covered Clay pot uncovered Jerry can (covered) Jerry can (uncovered) Drum (covered) Drum (uncovered) Plastic bottles Other (specify)
26	Is there any visible separation of water for drinking and water for other household activities?	Yes No
Section 4: Food Hygiene and Storage		

27	Where are clean cooking utensils stored?	In a basin uncovered In a basin covered On a shelf/rack In a cupboard On the floor Directly on a stool/chair Other (specify)
28	Where are fresh fruit and vegetables stored?	In a basin uncovered In a basin covered On a shelf/rack In a cupboard In a fridge On the floor Other (specify) None available
29	Where are meat and meat products stored?	In a basin uncovered In a basin covered On a shelf/rack In a cupboard In a fridge In a freezer On the floor Other (specify) None available
30	Is there any cooked food available in the house?	Yes No (go to Q31)
30a	Is it covered?	Yes No
31	Where does cooking take place?	Kitchen inside the house External Kitchen Veranda Household yard
32	Are there any animals near the cooking areas?	Yes No (go to Q33)
32a	Can they come into contact with any of the food being stored or prepared?	Yes No
Section 5: Household Environment		
33	Where do the household dispose of rubbish?	In a household bin collected from residence Deposited in communal bins and collected Placed in a rubbish pit next to house Placed in a communal rubbish pit Burned Thrown in a drain/open area Other (specify)

34	Is there any standing water around the house? (e.g., accumulation of rainwater or poor drainage)	Yes No (go to Q35)
34a	Were children playing or touching this standing water?	Yes No
34b	Were animals in contact with this standing water?	Yes No
35	Are there any open drains within the household yard?	Yes No (go to Q36)
35a	Were children playing or touching the drains?	Yes No
35b	Were animals in contact with the drain?	Yes No
36	You have completed data collection for this participant. Please thank them for their time.	
37	Staff signature	
38	Time and Date	MM:HH DD/MM/YYYY